
Country Policy Review and Analysis

Methodology Report – Revised 2018

EUROPEAN AGENCY
for Special Needs and Inclusive Education

COUNTRY POLICY REVIEW AND ANALYSIS

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The European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (the Agency) is an independent and self-governing organisation. The Agency is co-funded by the ministries of education in its member countries and by the European Commission via an operating grant within the European Union (EU) Erasmus+ education programme (2014–2020).

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

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The contributions to the Country Policy Review and Analysis activities of the Agency Representative Board members and staff team members involved in the work to date, are gratefully acknowledged.

Extracts from the document are permitted provided that a clear reference to the source is given. This report should be referenced as follows: European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, 2018. *Country Policy Review and Analysis: Methodology Report – Revised 2018*. (S. Symeonidou, V.J. Donnelly, V. Soriano and A. Watkins, eds.). Odense, Denmark

With a view to greater accessibility, this report is available in accessible electronic format on the Agency's website: www.european-agency.org

ISBN: 978-87-7110-830-9 (Electronic)

ISBN: 978-87-7110-829-3 (Printed)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents the methodology and materials developed within the Country Policy Review and Analysis (CPRA) activities. This version of the report presents an update to the information presented in the [original Methodology Report](#) (European Agency, 2016). It covers the work now conducted in three phases of the CPRA work, involving the following countries:

Phase 1 pilot countries: France, Italy, Lithuania, Malta, Norway, Portugal, United Kingdom (England) and United Kingdom (Scotland).

Phase 2 countries: Belgium (French community), Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Slovakia and Spain.

Phase 3 countries: Belgium (Flemish community), Cyprus, Czech Republic, Poland, Serbia, Slovenia and Sweden.

The CPRA work's goal is to aid country reflection regarding the development of policy for inclusive education. It aims to act as a tool for stimulating discussion in the country concerned. CPRA's central focus is to analyse the available information about current country policy for inclusive education; the work does not in any way address the actual implementation of the policy being considered.

The CPRA work has been developed to provide a new form of individualised country information. This provides countries with a reflection on their current policy frameworks for inclusive education. It also offers them recommendations for priorities to be addressed that are specific to their country. CPRA provides a comprehensive, rich and focused source of information on policy for inclusive education in countries.

The CPRA activities began in late 2014. They have been implemented to analyse inclusive education policies in volunteer member countries of the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (the Agency). The work had the following objectives:

- Offering countries a new type of individualised policy analysis information
- Putting the Agency's work into the broader European and international policy context
- Using Agency findings and outputs in a different way
- Exploring the potential for developing a cross-country analysis of information on policies for inclusive education across several countries.

These objectives led to the CPRA work being designed initially as a pilot activity that has been developed **with** country policy-makers **for** country policy-makers. Based on the Phase 1 piloting activities, more countries volunteered to participate in two subsequent phases of the CPRA activities.

Over the three phases conducted to date, the CPRA methodology has developed via an **iterative process**. This process involves a team of Agency staff members and the participating country policy-makers.

CPRA represents a different way of working with and for Agency member country representatives. It is based on collaborative, co-development working procedures that aim to support a continuing learning and improvement process for all involved.

The CPRA results and recommendations are essentially addressed to ministries of education. They have the potential to be used according to national-level priorities and needs. It is also anticipated that the CPRA work outputs will contribute to international-level requests directed to ministries of education. These may be, for example, in relation to European-level work associated with Country-Specific Recommendations (CSRs) and international-level work linked to the reporting process for the United Nations *Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities* (UNCRPD) (United Nations, 2006).

The three main priorities within the Education and Training 2020 ([ET 2020](#)) strategic objectives (Publications Office of the European Union, 2016) and [European Council CSRs](#) (European Commission, no date) provide the policy context for the CPRA work.

Twelve **European-level policy measures** for the CPRA work were identified, and they were adapted in relation to inclusive education. These were then complemented with selected **thematic recommendations** from a number of Agency projects and activities. A multi-analysis framework has been developed by mapping the 12 measures to Agency recommendations.

[Annex 1](#) of this report presents the full analysis grid.

The analysis grid has been used to identify and record **Findings**. These short descriptive texts identify, in a non-judgemental way, whether there is information – from Agency and country sources – indicating the existence or non-existence of a policy initiative linked to a specific recommendation in a given country.

In addition to the analysis grid information, a synthesis section was developed. This provides a shorter descriptive text of the grid information and what it means in relation to policy development for inclusive education. It aims to provide a ‘snapshot’ of a country’s policy for inclusive education in relation to European-level policy goals, as outlined in the 12 measures.

The synthesis section uses an agreed framework for analysing the country analysis grid findings. The framework is based on the three **types of policy actions** that are in line with European-level work (notably the CSRs), as well as wider thinking about quality for education, namely: **prevention, intervention and compensation**.

[Annex 2](#) of this report presents the synthesis section.

The CPRA piloting work, conducted with the Phase 1 countries, resulted in an agreed analysis framework. This comprises the grid and synthesis sections and agreed procedures for analysing country policy information. Since then, the same analysis framework, with slightly revised working procedures, has been used with all participating countries (Phases 2 and 3).

These concrete results have been used to develop a cross-country analysis of policy approaches being taken in countries. This cross-country analysis has the potential to provide individual countries with comparative information to relate to their own approaches. It may also highlight shared areas of concern for policy-making across

countries. In the longer term, this work could potentially indicate trends and movements in policy developments and directions.

In mid-2018, there was a review of the CPRA activities to date. All country representatives and Agency staff members involved in the first three phases of the work participated. Based on the feedback received, it has been agreed that a **second cycle** of CPRA activities will take place. This will potentially involve the same group of countries, but working on development and review activities with revised tools and procedures.

INTRODUCTION

This short report presents the methodology and materials developed and used within the first three phases of the Country Policy Review and Analysis (CPRA) activities, conducted by the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (the Agency). The CPRA work's overall purpose is to aid country reflection regarding the development of policy for inclusive education. It aims to act as a tool for stimulating discussion in the country concerned.

The first phase of the CPRA activities began in late 2014. This served for analysing inclusive education policies in volunteer Agency member countries. The work had the following objectives:

- Offering countries a new type of individualised policy analysis information
- Putting the Agency's work into the broader European and international policy context
- Using Agency findings and outputs in a different way
- Exploring the potential for developing a cross-country analysis of information on policies for inclusive education across several countries.

Within its past Multi-Annual Work Programme, the Agency used country information collected through thematic project work to develop recommendations agreed with all countries. CPRA examines how these general recommendations for policy developed in projects apply within individual country situations.

During the first phase of work, a small team of Agency staff worked closely with Representative Board members (RBs) from eight volunteer countries. They developed and then trialled the CPRA methodology.

Four countries initially acted as a Pilot Group (PG) for the analysis activities: France, Lithuania, Norway and United Kingdom (England). Four other countries, acting as a Reference Group (RG), supported the piloting work: Italy, Malta, Portugal and United Kingdom (Scotland).

Both the PG and RG regularly provided feedback on and inputs to the on-going activities that are outlined in the following sections of this report. The eight RBs' contributions to the pilot work were crucial for developing the methodology and materials used in the CPRA work. The activities have been subject to an iterative process to improve both methods and materials.

Following a successful pilot phase, a second phase of CPRA was conducted. A third phase is on-going as of 2018.

The second phase of CPRA was conducted from 2017 to 2018. It involved the following countries: Belgium (French community), Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Slovakia and Spain.

The third phase is underway and is expected to be completed by the end of 2018. Phase 3 countries include: Belgium (Flemish community), Cyprus, Czech Republic, Poland, Serbia, Slovenia and Sweden.

The information in this document provides the rationale for the CPRA work, as well as details of the steps and procedures used. It also presents the frameworks used for collecting, analysing and synthesising countries' policy information.

Rationale behind the CPRA activities

The Agency developed the CPRA activities for the following reasons:

- The Agency has conducted numerous thematic analyses in the past. The results of these analyses provide a solid, extensive knowledge base in key areas of the field of special needs and inclusive education. Until now, the Agency has provided countries with general recommendations related to the results of specific projects. The CPRA activities are an opportunity to provide country-specific information linked to the recommendations generated in different Agency projects.
- The Agency's work needs to be placed within a European and international context. Results from Agency projects can contribute towards achieving the education and training objectives agreed by the European Ministers of Education and towards reports on Article 24 of the UNCRPD.
- The Agency is the only European-level organisation able to complete an evidence-based analysis of individual countries' policies for inclusive education. Such an analysis reflects each country's position against a range of **European-level policy measures** and may indicate areas for future development.
- Based on the analysis of individual country information, there is the potential to develop a cross-country analysis of countries' policies for inclusive education. Identifying areas of policy advancement, as well as areas where further development is needed, has clear benefits for national and European-level decision-makers. Such work can also help to identify challenges and trends over time.

In order to respond to the points above, the CPRA work has been designed and developed **with** country policy-makers **for** country policy-makers.

A new way of working *with* countries

The overall CPRA methodology has developed via an **iterative process** (European Agency, 2016) involving the whole CPRA team. Initially, this team comprised the eight RBs in Phase 1 and a core team of Agency staff members.

The team made all the decisions regarding methodology collectively. The whole team drafted, then reviewed and re-worked materials before implementation.

The working principles underpinning this iterative process were:

- The CPRA activities involve working with volunteers.
- The individual countries are the 'owners' of the work.

-
- CPRA entails a new form of Agency team-working, involving both country representatives and staff members.
 - On-going reflection on the CPRA team's ways of working was crucial for agreeing next steps and outcomes.

This different way of working with and for Agency member country representatives was based on collaborative, co-development working procedures that aimed to support a continuous process of learning and improvement for all involved.

A new way of working *for* countries

The CPRA work has been developed to provide a new form of individualised country information on policy for inclusive education. The activities aim to support policy developments by providing individual country policy analysis using an agreed framework of policy aims and actions. This policy analysis provides countries with a reflection on their current policy frameworks for inclusive education. It also offers them country-specific recommendations for priorities to be addressed.

These results and recommendations are essentially addressed to ministries of education. They have the potential to be used according to national-level priorities and needs. It has become evident that the CPRA work outputs can also contribute to international-level requests directed to ministries of education. These may be, for example, in relation to European-level work associated with CSRs and international-level work linked to the reporting process for the UNCRPD.

The information sources used in CPRA all exist within different national or European-level contexts. However, the way in which the Agency draws this information together and applies it in the CPRA activities is both new and unique.

1. THE COUNTRY POLICY REVIEW AND ANALYSIS WORK

1.1. A project framed by European objectives

The three main priorities within [ET 2020](#) and the [Council CSRs](#) (European Commission, no date) provide the policy context for the CPRA work. The priorities are:

1. Ensuring equal opportunities in education and training
2. Improving educational outcomes
3. Reducing dropout from general and post-compulsory education.

The three priorities are closely related to the two ET 2020 strategic objectives that the Agency's work directly supports:

- Strategic objective 2 – Improving the quality and efficiency of education and training
- Strategic objective 3 – Promoting equity, social cohesion and active citizenship (Publications Office of the European Union, 2016).

The Council CSRs identify a number of policy areas – measures – for countries to address to support policy development work in line with the strategic objectives.

The various measures indicated in the Council CSRs were re-framed to align them with the Agency's agreed vision of inclusive education systems: that 'all learners of any age are provided with meaningful, high-quality educational opportunities in their local community, alongside their friends and peers' (European Agency, 2015, p. 1).

Altogether, 12 **European-level policy measures**, adapted for inclusive education, were agreed upon for the CPRA work. These were:

1. to improve inclusive education and to ensure that good quality education is accessible for all;
2. to support improved co-operation, including greater involvement of parents and local community;
3. to develop monitoring strategies, establishing a comprehensive accountability and evaluation framework for inclusive education;
4. to improve the cost-effectiveness of the education system, combining efficiency, effectiveness, equity and inclusion;
5. to increase participation in good quality inclusive early childhood education and care and enrolment rates in pre-school education;
6. to improve student-focused measures, such as mentoring, personalised learning approaches and improved guidance;
7. to improve the school ethos (such as the creation of supportive learning environments, adapting learning environments to specific learning needs);

8. to reduce the negative effects of early tracking (the early streaming of pupils by ability into different types of provision or schools) and to reduce the extensive use of grade retention;
9. to support improvement in schools with lower educational outcomes;
10. to improve the quality of school staff, focusing on the quality of teachers, quality in continuing professional development, developing teacher competences and reinforcing school leadership;
11. to improve transition from education to work by increasing the coherence between employment incentives, education and vocational education and training (VET); improving the quality and accessibility of apprenticeships; promoting cross-sector co-operation; simplifying the systems of qualifications;
12. to improve educational and career guidance across all phases of inclusive education.

The 12 policy measures were identified and agreed upon as key levers for meeting international and European-level policy goals and for improving the quality of education systems for all learners. These measures pinpoint the areas where action must be taken to successfully implement a comprehensive policy on inclusive education.

1.2. A framework of policy measures and recommendations for analysing country policy

The 12 European-level measures were the starting point for developing a framework to examine individual country policy documents. However, the 12 measures in themselves were too broad for such an analysis. Therefore, they were complemented with selected **thematic recommendations** from a number of Agency projects and activities. A multi-analysis framework of measures and specific recommendations was developed by mapping the 12 European-level measures to recommendations developed within seven areas of Agency work:

- [Early Childhood Intervention](#) (ECI) (European Agency, 2010)
- [Teacher Education for Inclusion](#) (TE4I) (European Agency, no date-a)
- Key Principles for Promoting Quality in Inclusive Education: [Recommendations for Policy-Makers](#) (KP-policy) (European Agency, 2009) and [Recommendations for Practice](#) (KP-practice) (European Agency, 2011)
- [Mapping the Implementation of Policy for Inclusive Education](#) (MIPIE) (European Agency, no date-b)
- [ICT for Inclusion](#) (ICT4I) (European Agency, no date-c)
- [Vocational Education and Training](#) (VET) (European Agency, no date-d)
- [Organisation of Provision to Support Inclusive Education](#) (OoP) (European Agency, no date-e).

These Agency projects provide a lifespan perspective. They consider existing provision at all levels of education, including early childhood education, compulsory schooling and transition to work. The projects also support an examination of quality in inclusive education through the implementation of key principles for evidence-based policies for inclusive education.

Across all seven projects and activities, over 160 recommendations were collated. However, there was considerable repetition, such as recommendations relating to co-operation among stakeholders, parents' involvement, quality of teacher training, accessibility of learning materials, etc. Accordingly, a first task was to eliminate repetition. The final number of specific Agency recommendations used within the CPRA work was approximately 130.

These recommendations were then directly mapped onto the 12 measures within a framework – an **analysis grid** – for information-gathering. In order to connect the project recommendations to European-level measures, a rationale was developed in co-operation with the Phase 1 country representatives to re-work the framework to reduce repetition.

Recommendations were selected according to:

- **their alignment with international conventions or with ET 2020** – such as consistency with the United Nations *Convention on the Rights of the Child* (UNCRC) (United Nations, 1989), the UNCRPD and policies promoting inclusive education;
- **their importance in supporting the prevention of early tracking and school dropout** – such as recommendations highlighting family involvement, early needs identification, teaching and support practices aimed at empowering learners, effective mechanisms for ensuring high-quality transition across educational sectors and phases, and flexible resourcing systems promoting inclusion;
- **their relevance for promoting quality in education** – such as recommendations highlighting the role of learner-centred approaches, high-quality teacher training, schools' ability to meet a greater diversity of needs, and mechanisms for evaluating effectiveness and quality in inclusive education;
- **their relevance for supporting schools to meet learners' needs** – such as strategic plans at school level, accessible and flexible teaching and learning approaches, ensuring high expectations for all learners' achievement, and the existence of high-quality support.

Such an approach also required criteria for distributing the recommendations across the measures. Recommendations were distributed in relation to four criteria, outlined below.

The first was their **consistency**. Some recommendations relate consistently to fundamental principles underpinning inclusive education and reflect general issues highlighted by some measures. For example, Measure 1, which focuses on good quality inclusive education, seemed to be the most appropriate place for recommendations referring to:

- alignment with the UNCRPD;
- cross-sectoral or cross-territorial legislation and policy;
- the accessibility of learning materials.

The recommendations' **specificity** was another criterion. Some recommendations were very specific to the topic addressed by a certain measure. For example, many of those developed within the VET project are strongly connected to Measures 11 and 12. Several recommendations from the ECI project correspond with Measure 5. Many recommendations related to teacher education and training are inter-related with Measure 10.

The recommendations' level of **complementarity within each measure** was also considered. Within each measure, recommendations had to complement each other. This was to avoid overlaps and allow for a complete analysis of country inclusive education policies in relation to a measure. Within the final analysis grid, over-arching recommendations are presented first, followed by more specific points that support the over-arching recommendation.

The final criterion was the recommendations' level of **complementarity across measures**. Providing complementary information across measures was an additional focus when distributing recommendations within the measures. For example, a recommendation in Measure 5, stating that 'Policy clearly respects the rights and the needs of children and their families', complements the recommendation in Measure 2 that 'The full involvement of families in all educational processes is outlined in legislation and policy'.

Due to the focus on project recommendations and the specificity of the measures, the distribution of recommendations across the 12 measures was unequal. Distribution depended both on recommendations made within the projects and on the specificity of the measures. In particular, none of the project recommendations explicitly highlighted early tracking issues (Measure 8) or the improvement of schools with lower educational outcomes (Measure 9). Nevertheless, some project recommendations were indirectly related to these issues. In contrast, many projects included recommendations aimed at improving inclusive education to ensure that good quality education is accessible to all (Measure 1). Meanwhile, only a few focused explicitly on improving educational and career guidance across all phases of inclusive education.

The combination of the recommendations and the measures was presented within a grid template. This was used for recording relevant information on country policy as **Findings** – precise information from project country reports and country policy documents indicating the implementation of recommendations linked to the 12 measures.

[Annex 1](#) of this report presents the full analysis grid.

1.3. A collectively designed analysis procedure

The development of the analysis grid involved identifying and drafting the 12 measures, and mapping the re-worked Agency recommendations onto the measures. This was the result of an **iterative process** developed within the whole CPRA team – the eight Phase 1 RBs and the Agency staff members. All steps were agreed upon and implemented, then collectively reviewed and re-worked before further steps were taken.

This iterative process was central to trialling and agreeing the procedures for the actual analysis of country policy information.

In Phase 1, once the draft analysis grid of measures and recommendations was agreed, information was identified from the individual country thematic reports from the Early Childhood Intervention, Teacher Education for Inclusion, ICT for Inclusion, Vocational Education and Training, and Organisation of Provision projects. This process aimed to provide a clear indication that some form of policy initiative was in place in relation to a specific recommendation.

For Phase 2, country national overviews were used. For Phase 3, national overviews and some additional materials, such as Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) sources, were used.

Using the information available, the staff team drafted a grid for a single pilot country with findings – information that clearly showed that the country’s policies accounted for specific thematic recommendations.

The CPRA team then examined the completed grid. The team members worked in pairs to discuss the material’s relevance and usefulness against each recommendation. They suggested possible improvements to the wording of findings and considered other areas for improvement. This iterative process led to the re-drafting of the analysis grid and a process of further synthesising the thematic recommendations to avoid duplication and re-wording them to make them as precise as possible.

This process also led to the ‘expansion’ of some recommendations, where necessary. This involved presenting **supplementary information** in brackets and italic text after the recommendation itself. Supplementary information was provided to avoid misunderstandings and to support comparability in the final analysis.

The review process also led to the insertion of a new section – Section 1. Here, RBs were asked to insert text to identify their country’s **main priorities for education**, paying special attention to the development of inclusive education.

Using the revised analysis grid, the CPRA team analysed the project country reports for all pilot group countries to identify and record the findings. It was agreed that findings would be linked to seven agreed criteria underpinning the information provided within the analysed reports:

1. **Existing legislation**, in order to relate inclusiveness to the rights of learners and their families
2. **Policy statements**, outlining the inclusiveness of education policies in light of the commitment to build capacity in mainstream education
3. **Requirements outlined to schools**, describing the commitments required from school stakeholders to ensure that inclusive education is embedded within schools’ policies and strategic action plans
4. **Quality assurance mechanisms**, supporting high-quality inclusive education policies and practices
5. **Tools and guidance**, empowering stakeholders to be innovative and inclusive on a daily basis
6. **Existing standards**, supporting practice that aims at high expectations for all learners, as well as effective and equitable education systems

7. **Monitoring mechanisms** (e.g. existing data) to ensure effectiveness, quality, equity and cost-effectiveness.

The first four of these criteria refer to types of policy directives. The final three refer to strategies for policy implementation and monitoring.

Two kinds of findings were identified:

- **General findings** that were considered to apply across the education system
- **Examples** that were considered to only apply to a specific thematic area, presenting innovative projects reflecting trends in policy changes towards more inclusive education systems.

In the analysis grids, findings were presented as a short extract from the country thematic project report and a citation (project title [abbreviations as in Section 1.2](#) and country report page reference). Examples were presented separately, with the text clearly marked as an example.

The findings are essentially descriptive; they identify, in a non-judgemental way, whether there is information indicating the existence or non-existence of a policy initiative linked to a specific recommendation in a given country.

The CPRA work's central focus is to analyse the available information about current country policy for inclusive education – it does not in any way address the actual implementation of the policy being considered.

1.4. The importance of country updating work

In all phases, Agency staff members worked in pairs to complete the analysis grids. This pairing involved an initial draft from one staff member, with the second staff member checking for consistency before a final draft was agreed. This process supported greater consistency and accuracy within and between country analyses.

The completed draft grids were sent to each country's RB for comment and **updating**. RBs were asked to provide updated policy information, in line with the seven criteria listed above. Updates included deleting and amending existing information, providing new information and reducing any repetition of findings.

Finally, RBs were asked to provide **evaluative comments** for each measure. These comments describe perceived challenges or areas for development, as well as relevant planned next steps and or/scheduled policy initiatives.

The staff members then checked the updated grid. Once the final analysis was agreed, the initial information and updated information were merged into a final document with overall country information.

Within the first pilot phase work, the process outlined above was initially completed with the four pilot group countries. Based on their inputs and agreements, the procedures were revised, improved and then repeated with the four reference group countries of Phase 1 and, later on, with all participating countries of all three phases.

The final analysis grids were comprehensive and detailed. A decision was made to also provide a summary of the overall policy analysis information for each country. The following section describes this stage of the CPRA work.

2. SYNTHESIS OF COUNTRY ANALYSIS INFORMATION

The CPRA work aims to aid country reflection and discussion regarding policy development. In line with this, it was agreed to develop a **synthesis** of the overall analysis.

The synthesis section aims to summarise the policy information presented in the full grid and provide a 'country profile' of policy approaches being taken in relation to the measures. It provides a short description of the information in the grid and sets out key points with regard to policy development for inclusive education. It aims to provide a 'snapshot' of a country's policy for inclusive education in relation to European-level policy goals, as outlined in the 12 measures.

The development process and structure for the synthesis was discussed and agreed with the Phase 1 pilot and reference group countries. Country views on the format and style of the synthesis differed, but all agreed about its usefulness for their respective ministries. The CPRA team took account of their views and incorporated feedback into each individual synthesis section.

Following feedback from the Phase 1 countries about the use of the synthesis section, Phase 2 and 3 countries also agreed to the drafting of such a section and the same procedures were used.

2.1. Developing the synthesis section

The synthesis section is drafted using the three **types of policy actions** that are in line with European-level work (notably the CSRs), as well as wider thinking about quality for education: namely **prevention, intervention and compensation**.

For each of the 12 policy measures used in the analysis grid to be effectively and comprehensively implemented, a balance of prevention, intervention and compensation policy initiatives must be in place. Depending on the focus of each measure, this balance may necessarily move further towards prevention, intervention or compensation policy actions.

Inclusive education systems are most effectively supported by a complementary combination of prevention, intervention and compensation policy actions. The goal of inclusive education systems is supported by policy actions that are designed to:

- **prevent** different forms of educational exclusion before they happen;
- **intervene** to ensure that good quality inclusive education is available for all learners at all times;
- **compensate** with specific actions and provision when prevention and intervention are not enough to ensure learners' needs are adequately met in inclusive settings.

Long-term, sustainable developments towards inclusive education systems can be seen as a combination of these three approaches in order to provide high-quality education for all learners, including those requiring additional support. A country's journey to an effective and equitable inclusive education system can be identified by movements away from

mainly compensatory policy actions, towards more intervention- and prevention-focused policy actions.

2.2. P-I-C coding of the analysis grid findings

The findings in each country's analysis grid were identified and categorised. They were then coded (using a three-colour coding system) as having the main policy purpose of prevention (P), intervention (I) or compensation (C). The P-I-C identification was based on the measure's perceived policy purpose. It used an operational definition of P-I-C actions agreed with the eight Phase 1 country RBs as a guide, and verified with all volunteer countries in the process:

- **Prevention** – policy initiatives that aim to *avoid* educational exclusion and longer-term social exclusion, before these issues emerge (for example, anti-discrimination legislation promoting a rights approach, avoidance of disabling policies that lead to gaps in provision, lack of qualifications, etc.).
- **Intervention** – policy initiatives that *support* the effective implementation of inclusive education (for example, the existence of clear policies leading to high-quality flexible support systems for mainstream education).
- **Compensation** – policy initiatives that *address* the inability of legislation and/or provision to support meaningful inclusive education for all learners (for example, separate educational programmes or provision, support for failing schools, second-chance educational programmes).

The terms in bold and italics in each operational definition indicate the essential focus of each policy approach.

As with the completion of the grid, two staff members worked collaboratively to complete this analysis work for each of the eight Phase 1 countries. Both the findings in the grid, as well as the information in 'Section 1: Country priorities for education', were P-I-C coded. The same process was followed in all three phases.

The country RB checked and approved this coding. Then, the overall profile of policy initiatives was written up as a summary providing a 'country profile' of approaches being taken in relation to each of the 12 measures.

The final section of the synthesis provides a **summary of areas of strength and areas for development**. This section takes a 'time-span' approach and summarises where the country currently is on its journey towards inclusive education. It is framed around the P-I-C model and five evaluative questions for policy-making that were collaboratively formulated by the Phase 1 country representatives:

Prevention

1. Do policy initiatives for an inclusive education system in [the country concerned] take all learners into account?
2. Do policy initiatives in [the country concerned] safeguard the rights of all learners to high-quality inclusive education?

-
3. Do policy initiatives in [the country concerned] promote the active participation of learners and their families in decision-making that affects them?

Intervention

4. Do policy initiatives in [the country concerned] monitor, evaluate and secure the effective implementation of an inclusive education system?

Compensation

5. Do policy initiatives in [the country concerned] identify and address barriers to the inclusive education system?

[Annex 2](#) of this report presents the template for the synthesis section.

3. BUILDING ON THE CPRA WORK

This revised version of the *Methodology Report* has been prepared during the third phase of the CPRA activities. It therefore takes full account of the first two phases of work.

The CPRA work so far has resulted in:

- an agreed analysis framework comprising the grid and synthesis sections;
- agreed procedures for analysing country policy information;
- an agreed format and style for the synthesis section;
- completed analysis grids for 15 countries, which can be accessed via the [project web area](#) (European Agency, no date-f);
- completed synthesis sections for 15 countries;
- a cross-country analysis of the policy approaches taken in the 15 countries in Phases 1 and 2.

In June 2018, an interim review meeting was held with countries participating in Phases 1, 2 and 3. In this meeting, the representatives of the participating countries stated that the CPRA work:

- helped the countries to reflect on national policies;
- provided a new framework for thinking about policy and policy-making;
- encouraged collaboration among policy-makers;
- facilitated countries to use the CPRA work for other purposes (e.g. present their policy at international level and prepare reports for international use).

3.1. Possible next steps

The participating countries' representatives provided valuable feedback and ideas to consider in the further development of CPRA activities. In particular, they suggested building upon the following four areas:

1. Use the P-I-C framework in future CPRA and Agency work

The P-I-C framework proved to be very useful in analysing policy approaches. It also encouraged countries to reflect on the balance of their policies (e.g. consider ways to improve the balance between prevention and intervention approaches). The P-I-C framework might potentially be used in future policy-oriented Agency projects.

2. Develop the cross-country analysis to include all participating countries from the first cycle

In order to maintain consistency for the cross-country analysis, tools and procedures remained the same during the first cycle (three phases to date). The cross-country analysis has the potential to provide individual countries with comparative information to relate to

their own approaches. It may highlight shared areas of concern for policy-making across countries. The cross-country analysis for the countries in the first cycle will not focus on – or name – individual countries. It will provide information on the common patterns of approaches that countries are taking in relation to the measures and specific thematic recommendations. In the longer term, this work could potentially indicate trends and movements in policy developments and directions.

3. Integrate CPRA activities into the wider Agency work programme

The CPRA work will both be informed by and impact upon other areas of Agency work. Outcomes, findings and recommendations from Agency thematic project work will be integrated into the CPRA analysis framework. Most importantly, the lessons learned from the CPRA focus and working procedures will inform the wider Agency work programme.

4. Consider a second cycle of activities based on CPRA

Based on the findings and experiences of the current CPRA work, there will be further reflections and discussions on how best to support countries that participated in the first cycle to engage in a process of self-evaluation that will enable them to reflect on changes since the first CPRA cycle.

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ANNEX 1: ANALYSIS GRID

Section 1: Country priorities for education

The text below presents the main country priorities in the field of education, with special attention to the development of inclusive education.

Country priorities

Section 2: Analysis of findings

Measure 1: To improve inclusive education and to ensure that good quality education is accessible for all

Agency recommendation	Findings
<p>1.1 There is a clearly stated policy for the promotion of quality in inclusive education.</p> <p><i>(Policy aims to widen access to education and to promote full participation and opportunities for all learners vulnerable to exclusion to realise their potential. Policy outlines how education policy-makers need to take responsibility for all learners.)</i></p>	
<p>1.2 Legislation and policy are consistent with the principles of the UNCRC and the UNCRPD.</p> <p><i>(Legislation and policy uphold the right of all learners to full participation in school with their own local peer group.)</i></p>	
<p>1.3 The concept of inclusion is clarified in education policy as an agenda that increases quality and equity for all learners.</p> <p><i>(Policy aims to address underachievement of all vulnerable groups, including children with disabilities.)</i></p>	
<p>1.4 Legislation and policy for inclusive education is cross-sectoral.</p> <p><i>(Policy outlines procedures to ensure the efficient co-ordination of services, as well as clearly defining roles and responsibilities.)</i></p>	
<p>1.5 There is a long-term multi-level policy framework for implementing quality inclusive education at national, regional and/or organisational levels.</p>	
<p>1.6 Policy outlines how education policy-makers need to take responsibility for all learners.</p>	

Agency recommendation	Findings
1.7 Policy has the goal of supporting all teachers to have positive attitudes towards all learners.	
1.8 Policy requires learning materials to be accessible.	
1.9 Policy describes an effective framework of support for schools to implement inclusive education. <i>(Support structures focus on different forms of educational resource centres that are locally organised to offer support to individual or clusters of schools.)</i>	
1.10 Policies outline a continuum of support for children and young people in schools, to meet the full diversity of learners' needs.	
1.11 Policy outlines strategies for awareness-raising with all stakeholders in inclusive education.	
1.12 Policy outlines the development of the role of special schools as a resource to increase the capability of mainstream schools and improve support for all learners. <i>(The specialist knowledge and skills of special schools/resource centres are maintained and further developed so as to enhance support for learners, such as those with low-incidence disabilities.)</i>	

Measure 1 evaluative comments

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Measure 2: To support improved co-operation, including greater involvement of parents and local community

Agency recommendation	Findings
2.1 The full involvement of families in all educational processes is outlined in legislation and policy.	
2.2 Policy for inclusive education places learners and their families at the centre of all actions.	
2.3 Sharing information among professionals and families is a policy priority.	
2.4 Policy has the goal of supporting parental interaction and communication with professionals.	
2.5 Schools are expected and supported to involve a wider range of partners and foster formal and informal networks that support their practice.	

Measure 2 evaluative comments

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Measure 3: To develop monitoring strategies, establishing a comprehensive accountability and evaluation framework for inclusive education

Agency recommendation	Findings
3.1 Policy describes clear mechanisms to evaluate effectiveness and quality in inclusive education.	
3.2 Monitoring procedures ensure that inequalities in access to educational resources at regional or organisational levels are addressed.	

Agency recommendation	Findings
3.3 Accountability measures that impact upon educational professionals' work reflect the importance of wider learner achievements.	
3.4 Policy outlines common standards for service and provision evaluation for use across health, education and social services.	
3.5 Policy outlines how to involve families in the process of evaluating quality of services.	
3.6 Policy describes mechanisms to evaluate demand for services.	
3.7 Policy supports opportunities for school teams to evaluate their practice through involvement in research and development activities.	

Measure 3 evaluative comments

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Measure 4: To improve the cost-effectiveness of the education system, combining efficiency, effectiveness, equity and inclusion

Agency recommendation	Findings
4.1 National-level inclusive education strategies are linked to long-term financial support.	
4.2 Funding policies and structures provide flexible resourcing systems that promote inclusion.	

Agency recommendation	Findings
4.3 There are long-term funding commitments to support collaborative initiatives between various school-based, resource centre and research teams.	
4.4 Policy outlines mechanisms for systematic data collection on expenditure and implementation that informs cost-effectiveness issues.	

Measure 4 evaluative comments

Measure 5: To increase participation in good quality inclusive early childhood education and care and enrolment rates in pre-school education

Agency recommendation	Findings
5.1 Policy clearly respects the rights and the needs of children and their families.	
5.2 Support is available for families to recognise and understand the needs of their child. <i>(Support focuses upon what is in the child's best interests.)</i>	
5.3 Policy outlines how ECI services should be provided for children and families as early as possible and as quickly as possible, following identification of need.	
5.4 Policy states that, in risk situations, the child's rights should come first.	
5.5 Policy measures and guidelines clearly define quality standards for early childhood services and provision.	

Agency recommendation	Findings
5.6 Early childhood guidance is developed jointly by departments of health, education and social services.	
5.7 Policy for early childhood services supports cross-sectoral, multi-disciplinary working at regional and local levels.	
5.8 Policy ensures there are pre-school places offered to children coming from ECI services/provision.	
5.9 Policy outlines how cost-free services/provision are made available for families.	
5.10 Policy ensures the same quality of service irrespective of differences in geographical location. <i>(Such as isolated or rural areas.)</i>	

Measure 5 evaluative comments

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Measure 6: To improve student-focused measures, such as mentoring, personalised learning approaches and improved guidance

Agency recommendation	Findings
6.1 High expectations for all learners' achievements underpin policy for inclusive education.	
6.2 Policy outlines that learners' voices should be listened to in decision-making that affects them.	
6.3 Teaching, support and guidance have the goal of empowering all learners.	

Agency recommendation	Findings
6.4 Appropriate educational support is available as necessary and is fit for purpose in meeting personal learning needs.	
6.5 The learning process is based on flexible curricula based on learner-centred approaches and the development and implementation of individual learning plans as necessary.	

Measure 6 evaluative comments

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Measure 7: To improve the school ethos (such as the creation of supportive learning environments, adapting learning environments to specific learning needs)

Agency recommendation	Findings
7.1 Policy supports school leaders to value diversity among staff as well as learners, encourage collegiality and support innovation.	
7.2 Policy outlines the responsibility of school leaders to effectively communicate their vision for inclusive education to the school teaching team and wider school community.	
7.3 Policy aims to ensure the recruitment of teaching staff from diverse backgrounds, including those with disabilities.	

Agency recommendation	Findings
7.4 Policy supports schools to ensure teaching staff are able to meet diverse learning needs. <i>(Teaching staff have competence and expertise to develop individual plans, implement learner-centred approaches and support learners in personalised learning.)</i>	
7.5 The school ethos and culture is guided by school strategic plans that have high expectations for the academic and social achievements of all learners.	
7.6 School strategic plans describe how universal design for learning approaches are used to provide individualised learning tools and opportunities.	
7.7 School strategic plans stipulate that all learners are entitled to be active participants in the life of the school and community.	
7.8 School strategic plans have clear statements on the value of diversity.	
7.9 School strategic plans describe mechanisms for shared leadership, teamwork and collaborative problem solving.	

Measure 7 evaluative comments

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Measure 8: To reduce the negative effects of early tracking (the early streaming of pupils by ability into different types of provision or schools) and to reduce the extensive use of grade retention¹

Agency recommendation	Findings
8.1 Legislation across relevant public sectors has the goal of ensuring educational services enhance developments and processes working towards equity in inclusive education.	
8.2 Policy outlines how support structures that impact upon inclusive education are diverse and easily available. <i>(Support structures prevent early tracking and streaming of pupils at an early age.)</i>	
8.3 Assessment mechanisms are in place to identify the support needs of learners at an early stage.	
8.4 Data is available relating to learners' rights to age-appropriate education.	

Measure 8 evaluative comments

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¹ Early tracking means the early streaming of pupils by abilities into different types of provision or school; this includes placing children into separate schools. The extensive use of grade retention means holding pupils back to repeat school years, instead of providing flexible individual support.

Measure 9: To support improvement in schools with lower educational outcomes

Agency recommendation	Findings
9.1 Clear mechanisms exist to identify schools with lower educational outcomes. ²	
9.2 Policy outlines how methods of assessment, inspections and other accountability measures contribute to school improvement processes. <i>(Accountability measures support inclusive practice and inform further improvement of provision for all learners.)</i>	
9.3 Policy aims to increase the capacity of all schools to meet a greater diversity of needs and support learners within their local communities. <i>(Schools are supported to use innovative teaching methods, practical learning approaches and individual plans, focusing on learners' capabilities.)</i>	
9.4 Policy outlines clear incentives for schools to take all learners from their local community.	
9.5 Policy requires school strategic plans to outline preventive educational action against dropouts. <i>(Including necessary measures so that learners who become disengaged find new educational alternatives.)</i>	

Measure 9 evaluative comments

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² This recommendation does not come directly from the Agency work covered in the CPRA activities. A number of project recommendations have implicitly, but not explicitly, referred to this issue. However, the piloting work and detailed discussions with PG countries showed it is necessary to have this explicit recommendation linked to this measure.

Measure 10: To improve the quality of school staff, focusing on the quality of teachers, quality in continuing professional development, developing teacher competences and reinforcing school leadership

Agency recommendation	Findings
10.1 Policy outlines how all school staff develop the skills to meet the diverse needs of all learners. <i>(Appropriate training and professional development is provided to all school staff, including teachers, support and administrative staff, counsellors, etc.)</i>	
10.2 Policy supports the development of high-quality and appropriately trained teacher educators. <i>(With improvements in recruitment, induction and continuing professional development.)</i>	
10.3 Policy supports flexible training opportunities in initial and continuing professional development, for all teachers. <i>(Schools and teacher education institutions will work together to ensure good models in practice schools and appropriate placements for teaching practice.)</i>	
10.4 All teaching staff are supported and develop a clear understanding of effective learning strategies. <i>(Such as learning to learn and active learning approaches.)</i>	
10.5 Policy supports schools to develop strategic plans of staff training in inclusive education.	
10.6 Policy outlines the specialised training pathways for specialists who support school communities to implement inclusive education.	
10.7 Policy supports research into the effectiveness of different routes into teaching. <i>(Including course organisation, content and pedagogy to best develop the competence of teachers to meet the diverse needs of all learners.)</i>	

Measure 10 evaluative comments

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Measure 11: To improve transition from education to work by increasing the coherence between employment incentives, education and VET ; improving the quality and accessibility of apprenticeships; promoting cross-sector co-operation; simplifying the systems of qualifications

Agency recommendation	Findings
11.1 Policy ensures that VET programmes should address labour market skill requirements.	
11.2 Policy aims at matching labour market skill requirements and learners' skills, wishes and expectations.	
11.3 Policy outlines the development of partnerships and networking structures. <i>(Partnerships with a pool of local employers to ensure close co-operation with regard to learners' supervised practical training and finding employment after graduation.)</i>	
11.4 Policy outlines how transition from education to employment is supported by adequate provision.	
11.5 Policy supports the availability of meaningful VET options for learners to choose from.	
11.6 Policy supports the availability of supervised practical training.	
11.7 Policy outlines how sustainable employment opportunities are supported through the availability of appropriate, on-going support.	
11.8 Policy outlines how VET programmes are reviewed periodically. <i>(Both internally and/or externally in order to adapt to current and future skill needs.)</i>	

Measure 11 evaluative comments

Measure 12: To improve educational and career guidance across all phases of inclusive education

Agency recommendation	Findings
12.1 Policy outlines the mechanisms for ensuring effective transition across educational sectors and phases. <i>(There are well-organised transition processes among services to ensure continuity in the support required when learners move from one form of provision to another.)</i>	
12.2 Policy outlines how career counsellors/officers support learners and employers regarding employment possibilities. <i>(Support is provided with job applications, inform and support employers and facilitate contact between both parties.)</i>	

Measure 12 evaluative comments

ANNEX 2: SYNTHESIS SECTION

This ‘synthesis section’ presents a descriptive summary of the findings presented in the CPRA grid for [the country concerned]. It aims to present a ‘country profile’ of policy approaches being taken. This provides a ‘snapshot’ of [the country concerned]’s policies for inclusive education in relation to the European-level policy goals (the 12 measures) and what this means with regard to policy development for inclusive education.

The findings – from Agency reports and the updated country information – presented in the grid have been categorised as taking an approach that is aimed at prevention, intervention or compensation. This identification is based on the measure’s perceived policy purpose in line with the operational definitions agreed with the pilot work RB members:

- **Prevention** – policy initiatives that aim to *avoid* educational exclusion and longer-term social exclusion, before these issues emerge (for example, anti-discrimination legislation promoting a rights approach, avoidance of disabling policies that lead to gaps in provision, lack of qualifications, etc.).
- **Intervention** – policy initiatives that *support* the effective implementation of inclusive education (for example, the existence of clear policies leading to high-quality flexible support systems for mainstream education).
- **Compensation** – policy initiatives that *address* the inability of legislation and/or provision to support meaningful inclusive education for all learners (for example, separate educational programmes or provision, support for failing schools, second-chance educational programmes).

The terms in bold and italics in each operational definition indicate the essential focus of each policy approach.

For the purposes of the CPRA work, compensation policy initiatives are understood to be those focusing upon system deficiencies and not learner needs, i.e. special educational needs/additional support that addresses a system ‘omission’ or lack of provision within an inclusive setting is compensation. Special educational needs/additional support that meets individual learner needs within an inclusive setting is considered a form of intervention.

The three policy purposes of prevention, intervention or compensation are complementary. They can potentially be used in different ways to achieve given policy goals.

1. Stated priorities for inclusive education

[The country concerned]’s stated policy priorities for education (as outlined in Section 1 of the analysis grid) ...

2. Policy actions in relation to the 12 measures

In relation to the policy initiatives taken by [the country concerned] in relation to the specific recommendations linked to the 12 measures (as presented in Section 2 of the analysis grid), the following approaches are suggested by information provided by [the country concerned].

Measure 1: Improving inclusive education and ensuring that good quality education is accessible for all

...

Measure 2: Supporting improved co-operation, including greater involvement of parents and local community

...

Measure 3: Developing monitoring strategies, establishing a comprehensive accountability and evaluation framework for inclusive education

...

Measure 4: Improving the cost-effectiveness of the education system

...

Measure 5: Increasing participation in good quality inclusive early childhood education and care and pre-school education

...

Measure 6: Improving student-focused measures

...

Measure 7: Improving the school ethos

...

Measure 8: Reducing the negative effects of early tracking and grade retention

...

Measure 9: Supporting improvement in schools with lower educational outcomes

...

Measure 10: Improving the quality of school staff

...

Measure 11: Improving transition from education to work

...

Measure 12: Improving educational and career guidance across all phases of inclusive education

...

3. Summary of areas of strength and for development

The use of the framework for analysis based on the concepts of prevention, intervention and compensation has helped to identify a number of evaluative questions for policy-making. These were formulated by the CPRA PG and RG representatives.

Each of these questions is addressed below using the policy information available for [the country concerned]:

- 1. Do policy initiatives for an inclusive education system in [the country concerned] take all learners into account?**
...
- 2. Do policy initiatives in [the country concerned] safeguard the rights of all learners to high-quality inclusive education?**
...
- 3. Do policy initiatives in [the country concerned] promote the active participation of learners and their families in decision-making that affects them?**
...
- 4. Do policy initiatives in [the country concerned] monitor, evaluate and secure the effective implementation of an inclusive education system?**
...
- 5. Do policy initiatives in [the country concerned] identify and address barriers to the inclusive education system?**
...

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